

SITE	YEAR	AREA	SECTOR	ELEVATION	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT
GPR	2010	B		Min: 62.0831 Max: 62.5633	1228 Natural ☐ Anthropogenic ☒

In cross-section? Yes No
 In elevation drawing? Yes No
 Photos: Yes No #: 772-793
 Photo Model: Yes No #:

DEFINITION: *square channel*

Covered by SU: 1230
 Fills SU:
 Filled by SU: 1221

HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED?
 Color Composition Compaction

FORMATION PROCESS
 Accumulation Construction Cutting Erosion Collapse Intentional deposition

INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (frequent, (medium), (rare)

Anthropic	Geological	Organic
☐ Pottery	☐ Tufo (specify)	☐ Charcoal
☐ Tiles	☐ Travertine	☐ Ash
☐ Amphorae	☐ Other Limestone	☐ Animal bones
☐ Dolia	☐ Basalt	☐ Human bones
☐ Mosaic tiles)	☐ Clay	☐ Animal teeth
☐ Mortar	☐ Sand	☐ Human teeth
☐ Coins	☐ Silt	☐ Shells
☐ Metal (specify)	☐ Pebbles (range)	☐ Other (specify)
☐ Collapse debris	☐ Gravel (range)	
☐ Glass		

SOIL/MATRIX
 clay ___% silt ___% sand ___%
 Granular Layered Cohesive

Compaction	Color
☐ Hard	☐ Black ☐ Brown
☐ Compact	☐ Gray ☐ Light Brown
☐ Friable	☐ Light Gray ☐ White
☐ Loose	☐ Yellow ☐ Red
☐ Soft	☐ Light Yellow
	☐ Other (specify)

UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)

Northern Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit
 Southern Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit
 Western Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit
 Eastern Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit

Depth: Original Not Original

STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE

Is equal to:	Is bound to (only for masonry):
Is abutted by:	Abuts:
Is covered by: 1230	Covers:
Is cut by:	Cuts: 1001 (bedrock)
Is filled by: 1221	Fills:

OBSERVATIONS
channel was detected at the very southwestern edge of trench B

DESCRIPTION
 Position within sector:
 Shape: *square, ca 2m long*

For layers complete this section:
 Surface (slope direction: visible inclusions):
 Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope):
 Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?):
 Nature of the interface with layer below: sharp diffuse commingled other (specify)

For cuts complete this section:
 Cut edges: rounded straight
 Cut sides straight concave convex sloping
 Cut bottom: flat concave irregular
 How is cut top edge? sharp rounded
 How is cut bottom edge? sharp rounded
 Observations:

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment:

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify) *channel is cut into bedrock*

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material: Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)
 Size: Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

Floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains: *length ca 2m, width 0,30m*

Description:

The channel was detected below SU 1203 and since it is covered with tufo slabs and sits right below the southern edge of the section the possibility of encountering it was rather limited! We were able to peer into the channel and

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

It is certain that we found the east-most edge of it. A large pit (SU 1223) was excavated in order to reach the bedrock. During the excavation of this "stairing pit" for the construction of the channel the earlier floor (SU 1173) was destroyed. The chronology of the impact is quite clear but not the date. Whilst peering into the channel one could see a "T-junction", meaning

INTERPRETATION

*another channel crossing our SU 1228. One could see light falling into this cross-channel from SW-direction and one could also feel very fresh and cold air steaming through the channel. The channel was dug as an open cast and covered afterwards with tufo slabs. If I would be much smaller I would have crouched into it to find out more about it. Interpretation: sewer? *

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

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